

Microwave assisted synthesis of 2,4-disubstituted pyrimido-[1,2-*a*]-benzimidazoles

M. B. Deshmukh*, A. W. Suryavanshi and S. A. Deshmukh

Department of Chemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur-416 004, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : m_deshmukhl@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : A new series of 2,4-disubstituted pyrimidobenzimidazoles were synthesized by conventional as well as microwave methods. The synthesized compounds exhibited moderate to good antifungal and antibacterial activities.

Keywords : 2-Aminobenzimidazoles, pyrimidobenzimidazoles, microwave assisted synthesis, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

The benzimidazole nucleus is found in numerous pharmaceutical agents with diverse range of biological properties. Benzimidazole and 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives represents the core structure of a number of biologically significant molecules. They play a significant role in pasmolytic dibazoles, neuroleptic pimozides, anti-histamine and astemizoles¹.

Although wide range of methods are available for synthesis of benzimidazoles², a real need exists for new simple procedures that support many kinds of structural diversity and various substitution pattern in the target molecules. The versatile applications of microwave method in the field of organic synthesis led us to synthesize by using this method a series 2,4-disubstituted pyrimidobenzimidazoles. We have developed this as a more viable process for synthesis of 2,4-disubstituted pyrimidobenzimidazoles.

Antibacterial activity :

The synthesized compounds **3a-e** have been evaluated for their biological activities by agar diffusion medium at 250 ppm against the *S. aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*-2510 using standard antibiotic drug *Streptomycin* sulphate and dimethyl formamide as a control of the solvent. Plates were incubated 48 h at 30 °C and the zones of inhibition were measured in mm have been incorporated in Table 3. All synthesized compounds were found to be moderately active against both types of bacteria.

Antifungal activity :

Similarly, the compounds were also tested for their

fungicidal activities against *Aspergillus nigar*-MTCC-2255, and *Penicillium chrysogenum*-NCIM723 using Greseofulvin as a control. By careful scrutiny of the results it revealed that the series of 2,4-disubstituted-pyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole **3a-e** exhibited the spectacular antifungal activities against test organism *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium chrysogenum*.

Table 1. Yields and reaction time used for the microwave assisted synthesis

Entry	M.p. (°C)	Microwave method		Conventional method	
		Reaction time (min)	Yield (%)	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)
3a	205	3	80	4	70
3b	190	3	75	4	70
3c	90	3	87	4	82
3d	275	4	78	4	72
3e	295	4	70	4	78

Results and discussion

The reaction of 2-aminobenzimidazole **1** with various substituted chalcones afforded 2,4-disubstituted-pyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole **3a-c**. The typical experimental procedure involves mixing of 2-aminobenzimidazole **1** and substituted chalcone **2a-e** in an open container in presence of EtOH/piperidine irradiated for 2–4 min with microwave irradiations, intervals of 30 s. For comparison a conventional method was carried out by refluxing it on water bath in presence of solvent. It was observed that the conventional method required longer reaction time and gave products in lower

Scheme 1

yield. The IR spectrum of **3** showed a sharp absorption band at 1623 cm⁻¹ due to C=N. The absence of NH₂ and C=O absorption bands at 3421 and 1663 cm⁻¹ respectively revealed the formation of 2,4-disubstituted pyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole. The formation of compound **3** was indicated by the appearance of a singlet at δ 7.4 ppm assignable to =CH of the pyrimidine ring. A comparative study in terms of yield and reaction time has been given in Table 1.

Table 2. Physical and analytical data of compounds 3a-e

Compd.	R	Mol. formula	Elemental analysis (%) :		
			Found (Calcd.)		
			C	H	N
3a	H	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₃	82.2 (82.1)	4.7 (4.6)	13.0 (13.1)
3b	OCH ₃	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ON ₃	78.6 (78.5)	4.8 (4.7)	11.9 (11.8)
3c	NO ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄	72.1 (72.0)	3.8 (3.7)	15.2 (15.1)
3d	OH	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ON ₃	78.3 (78.2)	4.4 (4.3)	12.4 (12.3)
3e	Cl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClN ₃	74.2 (74.1)	3.9 (3.8)	11.8 (11.7)

Experimental

The melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded using KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One FTIR spectrometer. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO on a Jeol-JMSD-300 spectrophotometer. Microwave irradiations were conducted in a domestic microwave oven [SAMSUNG M197DN (2450 MHz, 1500 W)].

Table 3. Antimicrobial activities of compounds 3a-e (Zone of inhibition in mm)

Compd.	R	Bacteria		Fungi	
		<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i>
3a	H	–	23	32	24
3b	-OCH ₃	–	18	28	26
3c	-NO ₂	6	28	28	34
3d	-OH	6	15	31	24
3e	-Cl	–	15	30	22
Streptomycin sulphate	–	15	34	–	–
Flucanazole	–	–	–	30	30
DMF	–	–	–	–	–

The starting material 2-aminobenzimidazole are commonly synthesized by reacting *o*-phenylenediamine with guanidine³.

Synthesis of [2-phenyl-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-pyrimido[1,2-*a*]benzimidazole (3b**) :** Conventional method : To a mixture of 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one **2b** (1 mmol) and 2-aminobenzimidazole **1** (1 mmol) in ethanol, catalytic amount of piperidine was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 h, cooled, filtered and recrystallized from ethanol.

Microwave method : A mixture of 1-phenyl-3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one **2b** (1 mmol) and 2-aminobenzimidazole **1** (1 mmol) in the presence of catalytic amount of piperidine in ethanol was irradiated in microwave for 2–4 min with intermittent irradiation (monitored by TLC). After cooling the product obtained was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol.

2,4-Diphenyl-pyrimido[1,2-a]benzimidazole (3a) : m.p. 205 °C; IR (KBr) : 1633 (C=N), 3056 cm⁻¹ (C-H); ¹H NMR (DMSO) : δ 6.6–7.91 ppm (15H, m, ArH); MS : m/z, 320 (M⁺), 297, 212, 174, 147, 147, 113.

2-Phenyl-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)-pyrimido[1,2-a]benzimidazole (3b) : m.p. 190 °C; IR (KBr) : 1608 (C=N), 3056 cm⁻¹ (C-H); ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 3.89 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.61–8.34 ppm (14H, s, ArH).

2-Phenyl-4-(m-nitrophenyl)-pyrimido[1,2-a]benzimidazole (3c) : m.p. 90 °C; IR (KBr) : 1623 (C=N), 3056 cm⁻¹ (C-H); ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 6.27 (1H, s, CH), 7.08–8.24 ppm (13H, m, Ar-H).

2-Phenyl-4-(o-hydroxyphenyl)-pyrimido[1,2-a]benzimidazole (3d) : m.p. 275 °C; IR (KBr) : 1630 (C=N), 3060 cm⁻¹ (C-H); ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆) : δ 5.6 (1H, s, OH), 7.1 (1H, s, CH), 7.23–8.2 ppm (13H, m, Ar-H); MS m/z, 336 (M⁺), 313, 279, 214, 157, 133.

The physical and analytical data has been incorporated in Table 2.

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